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Lessons Learned: Digital Semester for Engineering Courses at the Technische Universität Berlin

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ABSTRACT

From March 2020, Technische Universität Berlin switched to an emergency mode in an unprecedented situation for staff as well as students to prevent further spread of the Covid-19 disease. All German universities took similar precautions. Students were denied access to the physical facilities of the university for the rest of the year. For several weeks, the main body of the staff could not access the buildings either. The staff worked mostly from home and professors as well as teaching assistants started to prepare the summer semester 2020 to function as a complete virtual semester for the students. They had less than a month to rearrange teaching formats, develop digital learning materials, and implement technical solutions for the so-called “Digital Semester.” This paper presents examples of undergraduate engineering courses that were held during the Digital Semester in order to compare them to their former versions and to work out commonalities and differences. Thus, we draw conclusions that can be helpful for shaping future courses. The presented courses capture a broad range of different types of courses reaching from seminars and practical courses up to large courses of more than 800 students. In the end, we summarize the key findings with respect to identified pitfalls and positive transformations for this variety of different courses including recommendations on the technical usage of systems.

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Figure 1: Transforming face-to-face on-site lectures to remote digital education.

1 INTRODUCTION

In March 2020, due to the spread of Covid-19, the Technische Universität Berlin switched to an emergency mode in an unprecedented situation for staff as well as students to prevent further spread of the disease. All German universities took similar precautions. Students were denied access to the physical facilities of the university for the rest of the year. For several weeks, the main body of the staff could not access the buildings either. The staff mainly worked from home, and professors and teaching assistants started to prepare the summer semester 2020 to function as a complete virtual semester for the students. They had less than a month rearranging teaching formats, developing digital learning materials, and implementing technical solutions for the so-called “Digital Semester”. This paper’s general idea is to present examples of courses held during the Digital Semester to compare them to their former versions, work out commonalities and differences between these courses and their effects, and draw conclusions that can help shape future courses.

We present the shift to remote education for larger courses with several hundreds of students as well as for those with smaller numbers of participants like seminars (see Figure 1). For the larger courses, we present engineering courses about Modern physics and System programming. Both are challenged with the management of communication between students and teaching staff and provide chances for students to interconnect themselves through online services [1]. Differentiations are also depicted in their final exams, where the physics course shifted to online assessments, while the programming course applied regular exams that required personal attendance. Additionally, the execution of a computer science seminar, a course about numeric methods and a module on C++ programming for engineers are presented. All three are held typically for smaller groups than the other two courses, like 50 to 150 participants. The first consists of intensively interactive meetings discussing advanced research topics. The second combines classic lectures with the practice of programming in small groups. In the third, students practice the basics of coding. These courses undertook a transformation to ensure the same benefits of a small group, intensive, interactive form of meetings, but in an online manner and was challenged with higher numbers of participants than ever before. In the end, we summarize the key findings with respect to undertaken pitfalls and positive transformations for this variety of different courses, including recommendations on the technical usage of systems.

2 BEST PRACTICES OF ENGINEERING COURSES

The following five sections describe five different engineering courses and their rapid adaption to the remote teaching setup.

2.1 Introductory physics for engineers

For the Digital Semester, we had to modify fundamental elements of our course "Introductory Physics for Engineers," based on a traditional lecture, flipped classroom sessions, and tutorial sessions, including working on blackboards and experiments in small groups (5-30 participants), so far. Every year, up to 800 students of at least twelve bachelor degree engineering and all STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) register, of which about 80% are in the first year. Our course is accordingly an introduction to classical and modern physics. It can be viewed as a journey of key experiments, associated theory, and concepts, beginning in the winter term with classical Newtonian mechanics and ending at the end of the summer term with an introduction to quantum mechanics and solid-state physics. In 2017, we started to reform key course components, implementing new flipped classroom sessions, exercises, and concept tests, promoting conceptual understanding and reasoning; see Ref. [2] for details. All course material is also made available to students via the university's Moodle platform.

This recent modernization has received a substantial boost thanks to motivated and enthusiastic undergraduate teaching assistants during the university's shutdown. In addition to the lecture, which is now conducted online via Zoom and supported by videos and applets, we formed a video team with our undergraduate teaching assistants, producing at least two videos a week screencasts on essential topics. The 5 to 15 minutes long videos follow the curriculum and are embedded in weekly so-called learning guides, which help students through the material. In these learning guides, students are motivated to deal with the contents of the course actively. For example, they should read a chapter in a script newly created for this course (49 pages), watch the corresponding screencasts, and solve the weekly exercises. Afterward, the students must pass a self-test with concept-tests and algebra-based exam tasks before the subsequent learning guide is activated. We also implemented two mock exams that students took via the university's Moodle, like the final exams. Additionally, we created flashcards (Ankiapp.com github.com/ankitects/anki, 2021/8/3) to help students learn physics laws and typical diagrams on their PCs or cell phones to prepare for the exam. A guide to implementing microlearning videos, online exercises, and virtual exams into such a large university course and any other course typical for the STEM fields can be found in the conference proceedings at Ref. [3].

Not only, but primarily because our course mainly involves first-year students, communication among and with students is crucial for the (perceived) effectiveness of teaching and learning, which studies also suggest [4, 5]. Similarly, student's ability to self-organize is critical to their learning success. Therefore, we have built infrastructure for various social media to connect with students and encourage collaboration with their peers.

First, we made ourselves available as instructors for daily consultations via Zoom (two to four hours daily), in which students could discuss the lecture and the weekly exercises with us. In parallel, we set up a chat (Rocket.Chat github.com/RocketChat, 2021/8/3). The chat has the advantage that here exercises, videos, sketches, and mathematical content can be shared easily. Also, students can enter formulas and solutions or share them with the teaching staff as a photo of their worksheet, which is considerably more cumbersome during a Zoom session. In Zoom sessions, there are always multiple students listening and students have to be willing to share their thoughts and calculations with their peers, which can be awkward.

However, less than 10% of students took advantage of these offerings. In particular, participation in the video consultations dropped sharply in the middle of the semester and again rose sharply a few days before the exam. In contrast, we found that students communicated with their peers primarily through messenger channels, with about 200 students participating more passively than actively. Due to low demand, we reduced our weekly consultations to two hours, which led to a significant increase in demand. Suddenly, more than ~30% of students

participated in the consultations stimulating discussions. However, this is no comparison to the participation and dynamics during the on-site tutorials and flipped classroom sessions. It is needed to counter these difficulties, as students are left alone and lost during the semester, as we can see in the number of participants and reduced participation in the final exam.

Together with the lecture and office hours, the weekly assignments, mock exams, and the script form a framework that aims at intensive independent learning, which is rather unpopular among students. We tried to compensate for this by making ourselves available via social media and video consultations. On the other hand, the videos and lectures were very well received, and about a quarter more students participated than in the face-to-face lectures and exercises.

2.2 Introduction to Industrial Information Technology

The module "Introduction to Industrial Information Technology" is organized in the typical format of a lecture and a seminar. Whereas the lecture covers the broad field of industrial information technology, the seminar has been designed to teach engineering students the basics of C++ programming. Before the Digital Semester, the lecture was held as a classical weekly face-to-face routine on campus. For the seminar the roundabout 100 participants were split into four groups to attend their own seminar. Each seminar group was again divided into working groups of three. It was within these working groups that the students had to prepare a number of assignments throughout the semester. If the learning objectives were met was tested via weekly kahoot! quizzes on the one hand and a written exam at the end of the semester on the other hand, covering lecture as well as seminar content.

For the Digital Semester the lecture was held as a live stream at the gaming platform twitch.tv allowing for real-time student-teacher interaction via the chat function while recording the live stream to be uploaded as a video file into the Moodle course for the students. The seminar was turned into a video-based self-learning course. Creating the entire content as screencasts took a while. However, the production effort for a weekly screencast session was approximately the same as conducting the session face-to-face with four groups each, as had been done earlier. Therefore, the production could be realized along with the curriculum week by week. Still, the students had to form groups of three for the weekly assignments. However, due to rules of social distancing, the session exercises that had formerly been worked on as a team with one computer on site were now to be done individually at home. To guarantee regular contact between teaching staff and students despite working remote, individual weekly online consultation hours were defined for each team.

Those measures had a number of effects. The first visible effect was a 50% increase of enrolment compared to former courses. This might have been due to the fact that passing a course covering C++ is compulsory for many of the universities students and we were simply one of the first chairs offering an online version of such a course. The first lecture stream was even viewed by five times the number of people that usually sat in the lecture hall. We assume that among the participants were also some colleagues who wanted to get an impression of how other disciplines implemented online lectures. The number of participants soon dropped to the average percentage of participation known from the previous years. It is noteworthy that our students attended the live stream at the set dates although they had the option to view the recordings on the Moodle platform at any point in the follow-up. The number of students that actively used the chat function to ask questions was slightly higher than that of those who used to participate actively during the lectures on site. Therefore, it does not seem to have been the possibility to interact that made them attend the live stream. However, the Digital Semester required a great deal more self-structured learning of the students than they

were used to. We presume, they recognized attending the lecture at a given time each week as being helpful with regard to structuring their study activities.

Another effect was seen in the usage behavior of the seminar screencasts. The weekly screencasts were viewed an average of 3.5 times per participant. In the face-to-face seminar of previous years, this option for multiple presentation of the content did not exist. Although it used to be possible to ask questions directly in the seminar, which meant that uncertainties could be clarified quickly, those who had missed something used to find it difficult to get back into the explanations. Due to the online consultation hours, there was also a regular opportunity to clarify open questions in a small group during the Digital Semester. However, the students had to search for answers on their own until the consultation hour and deal with the material more actively, which apparently happened, for example, by watching the screencasts several times.

In addition, the students had to be more active than before in completing the exercises. While they still worked out solutions together in their groups, they each completed the programming exercises on their own. Previously, the often uneven distribution of prior knowledge or work efficiency among the students frequently led to group members with less prior knowledge or slower work speed taking a back seat during the exercises on the jointly used computer. By working on the exercises individually, everyone had to work at their own pace, which certainly had advantages for the learning process.

The individualized work mode and the option to repeatedly watch lecture, seminar and exercises resulted in a significantly higher percentage of enrolled students who took the exam than in previous years. At the same time, the failure rate decreased by almost 50% from 14.1% to 7.7% and the grade point average improved by almost half a grade from 3.1 to 2.7.

Overall, we have learned from the Digital Semester that students benefit from synchronous arrangements also in digital formats. The biggest advantage, however, is the individualization of the learning process.

2.3 Numeric methods in civil engineering

Up to 150 students attend the course “Numeric Methods in Civil Engineering” each year. According to the study schedule, they should be in their fourth semester when taking it. In the Digital Semester the traditional lecture was changed to a flipped classroom format: corresponding documents were released on the digital Moodle platform of the university and a meeting was scheduled usually a week after publishing the documents. Exercises in which the calculations had formerly been demonstrated in a way of a traditional lecture, were now given to the students as short video clips. Also a meeting for questions and further explanations was scheduled usually within a week. Both, exercise and lecture were evaluated in the week they were scheduled, asking our lecture students whether the documents/slides and the lecture notes were useful; and our exercises students if the shown approach (in PDF) and the video clips were helpful. The third question was “What was bad/left out or can be improved? Are there unanswered questions?”. Participation was optional and the feedback anonymous. Students frequently used the answer to question 3 to place own questions regarding the content prior to the upcoming meeting. This was helpful for preparing the meeting and making sure that the crucial points were understood. The evaluation was answered frequently in the first weeks of the course. During the semester the participation decreased, probably because there were only minor problems.

In addition to lecture and exercise, there are practical trainings for programming and to practice calculations every week. The group of students at each session counts 20 maximum.

The practical trainings are intended to take place at a computer pool. Due to the Digital Semester every student had to use his or her own device. The needed software is free and the requirements are relatively low for programming in java, but the provided help via tools like Zoom seemed like it was not as helpful or appreciated as in a presence meeting. The tasks and the solution were published in advance to the practical training. To create the same work atmosphere as at the practical training in the computer pools, the students were divided into groups. Each group consisted of three people and the tutor checked on every group regularly. Nonetheless, the attendance decreased over the course of the semester stronger than in former years.

The practical training was also evaluated with three questions every week like lecture and exercise. In the first question the students told us what they did as preparation for the practical training like watching the video clips of the exercise. The second questions asked about the difficulty of the training in their opinion. The answers of these two questions together were helpful for adjustments in the assignment. It is more likely for students to find the task harder when they are ill-prepared and this way it was easier to assess their feedback. The third question was the same as for lecture and exercise - we asked for suggestions to improve our content and if there are further questions.

The evaluation at the end of the course showed that a lot of students valued aspects such as fast responses to emails and the numerous possibilities to ask questions. Students profited from the fact that almost the entire course content was digitally available. Consequently, some stopped attending most of the live meetings and only came to prepare for the test. However, more students passed the course compared to former years and nearly all evaluation participants stated that they understood why this course is important for their studies.

2.4 System Programming

The course "System Programming" teaches theoretical concepts of modern operating system designs and provides practical experiments for hands-on experiences. It is an undergraduate course for more than 800 Computer Science and Computer Engineering students in their first year. The 12-week course consists of a series of weekly lectures for the large group of participants, while also providing more practical exercises for smaller groups of around 30 students in weekly sessions. The grading process is split into mainly two areas: Theoretical and practical. The theoretical concepts are assessed with a written exam, while for practical tasks, groups of four students are handed bi-weekly exercise sheets. The university's Moodle platform is used for distributing digital materials, handing in the exercises, and providing a digital discussion space for students in forums. In order to provide our best individual feedback, our teaching team consists of 17 persons, from out of which 14 cover the practical sessions and 3 the lectures and overall organization of the course.

All the sessions, which had formerly been conducted physically inside the university buildings, had to be digitalized. This has been carried out by producing video content for asynchronous learning and additional non-graded exercise material, as well as by providing additional digital space to discuss questions about the videos, combined with a live session, where students were able to ask questions about the content of the videos, similar to the flipped-classroom principle. Videos were newly produced for both lectures and practical sessions and uploaded weekly at the beginning of the week (Monday morning). For the rest of the week, the content of the videos of the current week was discussed during live sessions via Zoom. As additional materials, Multiple-Choice questionnaires (for each video around 10 tasks), were produced for students to self-assess their understanding of theoretical concepts explained in the videos. The grading process did not change much compared to pre-Covid-19 conditions: The practical

Figure 2: Situation for writing an exam with enforced rules writing in large air-conditioned rooms, increased distance, and wearing face masks due to Covid-19 pandemic.

tasks were distributed via the Moodle platform as well as the hand-in-process. The written exam was carried out on site in large exhibition halls with specialized rules (see Figure 2). The key rules were that students needed to wear masks for the whole duration staying in the building, and at least 2 meter of space between students needed to be ensured. All tables had to be disinfected before and after writing the exam. The exam took place in mid-August, where the numbers of new Covid-19 infections were low all over Germany.

Attending sessions was optional for the students, which led to just a small number of around 10%-15% of the students attending the live sessions, while more than 800 students handed in the bi-weekly practical tasks. Participation in the Moodle forum was less frequently used compared to pre-Covid-19 years, with 3-5 questions per video that were asked with this asynchronous offer. Also, the teaching personnel needed to adapt to the remote teaching setup, in which students obviously hesitated to ask questions at the beginning of the live sessions. Therefore, the format was adapted by showing key aspects of the videos in the beginning of the sessions, from which discussions arose much more frequently.

The number of watched videos and the number of used non-graded material (especially the MC tests) indicate the usability of our newly created digital material. The overall grades of the courses did not change significantly. Consequently, we consider that the production of new videos and further material was successfully applied.

2.5 The Software Horror Picture Show

The course "The Software Horror Picture Show" is a seminar mainly focused on topics concerning software errors, bugs, or failed projects related to such problems. Examples for such topics are the crash of the first Ariane 5 space launch vehicle, the crashes of the two Boeing 737 MAX, or even the virtual pandemic in World of Warcraft in 2005. Usually, 30 students enroll for the course. A weekly course meeting is used to present basics of how to present and write for the scientific community. The students carry out exercises and discuss the topics. Over the semester they give two five minute talks each, both on the same topic to allow them to incorporate the feedback of the first talk in the second. At the end of the semester, students give a 20 minutes talk each, followed by a discussion on the topic and participants hand in an additional essay on their topic.

For the Covid-19 edition of the course, instead of the usually about 70 applicants almost 200 students applied to participate in the course. Therefore, the course size was increased to 50 participants. The attendance phases were discarded. Instead, a course on the university's Moodle platform was used. Each week, the students could access screencasts explaining the basics of presenting and writing. The screencasts stayed online for the duration of the course. Additionally, a team chat using Mattermost was used for the course where the instructor answered questions. Most weeks, the students had to collectively work on an exercise on the collaborative platform Etherpad, e.g. answering questions on the quality of two given sources. As the students could see the answers of the other participants, they often discussed

or argued in these Etherpads. The five minute talks were handed in as self-filmed videos by the students, which worked very well. The final 20 minutes talk was given in small groups via Zoom conferences, therefore at least some discussion in-between students was possible. The final essay was handed in as in regular semesters in a digital form.

Overall, the course worked well in the Corona edition. However, the active participation and especially the discussion in the chat as well as concerning the final talks was far less lively. The exercises on the Etherpads were used very well and the comparison of results was an interesting factor, influencing the answers of the students. The grades of the students that participated were similar to the non-digital semesters.

3 LESSONS LEARNED

Summarizing the presented courses, the lessons learned are two-fold. At first we present key digital tools used for the interaction between teaching staff and students. Afterwards, we continue with the key overlaps of shared observations among the different courses, concluding the long lasting impact of changes also shaping the courses after the pandemic.

Table 1 presents different digital tools and applications for various needs in the interaction and communication between teachers and students. For most presented lectures, the key management platform Moodle was utilized for student enrollment, assignment of tasks, distributing material, etc. As Moodle is an open source platform, there exist a lot of freely available plugins. The main and most useful plugins applied in our lectures were: Quiz activity, CodeRunner, Course feedback, and Learning paths. While Quiz activity and CodeRunner are foremost interesting for examination purposes, Course feedback is applied for collecting anonymous feedback from students for the lectures quality assurance. Lastly, the plugin Learning paths provides the opportunity to establish guided organization and structure for self-paced learning. Live-sessions were carried out through the tools of Zoom, Twitch, and Jitsi. The diverse landscape of different tools was caused by the late establishing of high quality video streaming platform setups at the university. Most teachers had to setup own solutions, but switched soon to Zoom since it was the recommended platform for teaching for the Technische Universität Berlin. While live-sessions were carried out, the students were able to ask questions by using the chat systems from Zoom, Rocket Chat, and Mattermost. Platforms including chat systems like Zoom provide a beneficial combination offering an optimized environment without the need of additional screens. Lastly, Anki Cards are utilized to present students digital materials similar to conventional learning cards.

Table 1: Digital applications used for the communication between teachers and students.

Management Platforms	Live-Sessions	Chats	Additional Tools
Moodle (Plugins: Quiz activity, CodeRunner, Course feedback, Learning paths)	Zoom Twitch Jitsi	Rocket Chat Zoom Chat Mattermost	Anki Cards

All presented courses created additional recorded teaching materials like videos and screencasts. Key advantages results from the 24/7 provisioning of this material on the Moodle platform, enabling the students to repeatedly watch them and thus and learn in their own pace. The production of videos and screencasts is time-wise comparable to a teaching situation when the same content has to be presented several times a week. Further reusing such material for the following semesters increases the saving of time on the teachers' side. Then again, the change of single parts within a videos/ screencasts is much more difficult than changing single

slides within a PowerPoint slide-deck. The update gets even more complicated when new or different lecturers want to change parts of the video, as audio sequences and presentation styles might impact the quality of the video material significantly, ending up with producing the whole video over again. We propose to prepare screencasts showing slides without video- and audio-recordings of lectures. The audio should be added later when creating videos with long duration. Another option is to split longer video material in small chunks, which can be individually reproduced quickly.

When including the recorded/live videos and screencasts into the lecture, we presented different approaches leading to different findings. The replication of traditional lecture formats with fixed time slots per week for a presented live-stream was widely accepted in one course despite the option to watch the recordings at a later point in time. A possible explanation is that such fixed appointments helped the undergraduate students to structure their learning process and thus master the suddenly unusually high expectations regarding self-directed learning in the Digital Semester. Contrary, when applying the flipped-classroom concept with adding self-paced learning material with live-sessions to discuss the uploaded material, it led to a low rate of attendance (10-15%). We presume that the new flipped classroom format together with the transition of the learning setting from on-site to digital learning was overwhelming for first year students in undergraduate courses as such young students have little experiences in self-regulated learning [6].

Compared to pre-Covid on-site lectures and face-to-face consultation offerings, students attended less frequently digitally offered consultation hours and forums. Due to the lack of attendees, the offers for consultation were reduced each week, causing a rise in interest to the end of the semester. Hence, we propose to rather prepare some qualitative consultation offerings than overwhelm students with too many opportunities.

For the lectures, additional chat opportunities were established concurrently with the live session so that students could ask questions during the session. For such situations, the participation was greater compared to face-to-face lectures. This shows that live-sessions reduce the barrier to attending lectures compared to on-site lectures for which students have to come to the university.

Group work and group assessments were carried out also during the digital semester. The groups were able to establish connections and organizing their work with various digital tools like WhatsApp, Telegram, Overleaf, or Google Docs. Still, the assigned work was mostly carried out by individuals, while most of the group members had hidden in participation. In the future, we suggest taking the advantages of automated evaluations, provided by platforms like Moodle, to frequently ask for individual assessments instead of group assignments. By this, we hope to help students establish self-learning strategies who would otherwise tend to ignore their own learning needs as long as they can still pass the course without tackling that weakness. Nevertheless, we suggest to still include some group work to provide the possibility to connect and network even in remote working situations.

The changes introduced during the pandemic are going to influence how lectures will be organized and presented in the future. Especially rather short videos/screencasts with long-lasting content is going to be used in future courses. As has been shown, such newly introduced digital material is beneficial to students, allowing them to study in their own pace. Also didactic insights will change the way group work is organized and consultation offers are designed.

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